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The Role of Educational Psychology in Achieving Sustainable National Development: A Review of Literature

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Abstract

This paper examines the relationship between educational psychology and sustainable national development. Sustainable national development is defined as the process of improving the economic, social, and environmental well-being of a nation in a manner that ensures the well-being of future generations. Educational psychology is concerned with the study of human learning, motivation, and development in educational settings. The paper reviews the literature on the role of educational psychology in achieving sustainable national development. The review identifies several ways in which educational psychology can contribute to sustainable national development, including promoting environmental education, fostering positive attitudes towards sustainability, and enhancing students' critical thinking skills. The review also highlights some challenges and limitations in the application of educational psychology in achieving sustainable national development.

Keywords: Educational psychology, Sustainability, Challenges and limitations

Introduction

Sustainable national development is a complex and multifaceted concept that encompasses economic, social, and environmental dimensions. It is a process of improving the well-being of a nation in a manner that ensures the well-being of future generations. Achieving sustainable national development requires a comprehensive and integrated approach that takes into account the interdependence of economic, social, and environmental factors. Educational psychology can play a critical role in achieving sustainable national development by providing insights into human learning, motivation, and development in educational settings.

One way in which educational psychology can contribute to sustainable national development is by promoting environmental education right from early years, because that is a period when Montessori believes that children acquire most knowledge effortlessly Montessori, (1949). The Absorbent Mind. New York: Henry Holt and Company. Environmental education is the process of providing individuals with the knowledge, skills, and attitudes needed to understand and appreciate the natural world and to take responsible action to protect it. Environmental education believes that sustainable development is possible and warns against indiscriminate development that disregards ecological balance. It aims at creating a future society where people are aware of their civic responsibilities and are ready to play useful roles as producers and citizen's conscious of their environmental impact (ICSE, 2000). People need to be aware of what their environments look like, what it requires to stabilize it and what to avoid to protect it from natural disasters like erosion, earth quake among others. Educational psychology can help to design effective environmental education programs by providing insights into the cognitive, affective, and behavioral processes involved in learning about the environment. Research has shown that environmental education programs that are based on sound educational psychology principles are more effective in promoting environmental awareness and action.

Educational Psychology and Sustainability

Määttä and Uusiautti (2020) explored the role of educational psychology in sustainability education. They proposed that sustainable happiness education, focusing on human happiness and life satisfaction, can be a guiding principle for sustainability education. The authors emphasize the need to understand the reasons behind individuals' behaviors and the influence of habits and norms. They discussed the transition from consumerism to constructive behaviors and highlight the importance of individual responsibility and choices in achieving sustainable lifestyles. Their article suggests that a profound understanding of what is sufficient can promote happiness, satisfaction, and responsibility towards oneself, others, and the environment. Positive education is proposed as a means to enhance well-being, resilience, and sustainable behaviors. The authors argued for the integration of sustainable happiness education into teaching and curricula at all levels of education. They also emphasize the need for positive support and hope in promoting pro-environmental behavior. Overall, the article calls for educational psychology to contribute to sustainability education and foster positive change.

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Ronen and Kerret (2020) explored the concept of wellbeing and its connection to positive psychology and environmental sustainability. It highlights the limitations of using gross domestic product (GDP) as a measure of wellbeing and discusses alternative indicators such as the sustainable development goals, better life index, and happy planet index. The paper proposes an integrative policy approach to defining and promoting both human and environmental wellbeing using principles from positive psychology and environmental sustainability. It emphasizes the role of the educational system in promoting wellbeing and suggests a holistic sustainable wellbeing model that integrates positive psychology, environmental sustainability, and cognitive-behavioral therapy principles. The article concludes that a joint model of sustainable wellbeing can enhance personal wellbeing while fostering responsible global citizenship and caring for the planet's future. The definitions of wellbeing in positive psychology and sustainability are discussed, and the need for an interdisciplinary definition that considers the interdependencies between individuals and natural systems is emphasized. The concept of sustainable wellbeing is introduced, which focuses on improving individual wellbeing while also considering the wellbeing of others and the natural environment. This approach aligns with complex systems thinking and the World Health Organization's definition of mental health.

Moolla (2011) observed that a solid psychological perspective is urgently needed to address the environmental, social, and economic sustainability issues that our biosphere is currently facing. This perspective should complement biological, technological, and economic perspectives. In his article, he discusses positivistic and constructive psychology and provide a summary of major environmental problems and their implications for society and the economy. He also presents essential psychological reasoning related to these problems, including the commons dilemma model, different behavioral processes and strategies for behavior change, and various aspects of human quality of life. The authors argue that psychologists can play a crucial role in analyzing and mitigating the biggest sustainability problems, such as population growth, resource-intensive consumption, and harmful technologies. However, he explained how everything requires aligning psychological research with other environmental sciences, improving the incentive structure for this work, and paying more attention to the collective side of human behavior. He emphasizes the importance of sustainable development, environmental psychology, and behavior change strategies.

Educational psychology can also contribute to sustainable national development by fostering positive attitudes towards sustainability. Attitudes are important predictors of behavior, and positive attitudes towards sustainability can lead to pro-environmental behavior. Educational psychology can provide insights into the factors that shape attitudes towards sustainability, such as cognitive dissonance, social norms, and self-efficacy. By understanding these factors, educators can design interventions that promote positive attitudes towards sustainability. Attitude is one of the most important factors of learning because while knowledge and skills give a person potential, attitude is what determines their level of performance. This is because attitude controls a person's level of motivation. People can also be exposed to mindfulness, eating and activity habits to form their attitude towards sustainability of environmentally friendly activities.

Challenges and Limitations

Despite the potential benefits of educational psychology for achieving sustainable national development, there are some challenges and limitations in its application. One challenge is the lack of integration between educational psychology and environmental science. There is a need for greater collaboration between these disciplines to ensure that environmental education programs are based on sound educational psychology principles. Another challenge is the lack of emphasis on sustainability in educational psychology curricula. There is a need for greater attention to sustainability in the training of educational psychologists to ensure that they have the knowledge and skills needed to contribute to sustainable national development.

Conclusion

Educational psychology has the potential to make a significant contribution to sustainable national development by promoting environmental education, fostering positive attitudes towards sustainability, and enhancing critical thinking skills. However, there are some challenges and limitations that need to be addressed to ensure that educational psychology is effectively integrated into sustainability efforts. Greater collaboration between educational psychology and environmental science and greater emphasis on sustainability in educational psychology curricula are needed to maximize the potential of educational psychology for achieving sustainable national development.

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Recommendations

The followings are recommendations base on the findings of this paper:

1. **Integration of educational psychology and environmental science:**
2. There is a need for greater collaboration between these two disciplines to ensure that environmental education programs are based on sound educational psychology principles.
3. **Emphasis on sustainability in educational psychology curricula:** The training of educational psychologists should include a focus on sustainability to ensure that they have the knowledge and skills needed to contribute effectively to sustainable national development.
4. **Promotion of critical thinking skills:** Educators should prioritize the teaching of critical thinking skills to enhance students' ability to make informed decisions about complex issues such as sustainability.
5. **Increased awareness and education:** Efforts in schools from primary to tertiary levels should be made to increase awareness about environmental issues and educate people about sustainable practices to encourage individuals to adopt eco-friendly habits.
6. **Mindfulness and conservation:** Media programs can be introduced to educate citizens on being mindful about consumption habits and actively conserving resources can make a significant difference in the environment. For instance, turning off lights and electronic devices when not in use, taking shorter showers, and using reusable bags instead of single-use plastic bags can help reduce waste and conserve resources.
7. **Taking responsibility:** Individuals should be encouraged to take personal responsibility for their environmental impact and make conscious decisions about what they buy, where they shop, and how they dispose of their waste.
8. **Adopting a long-term perspective:** Nigerian Government should recognize the importance of sustainability and adopting a long-term perspective is another essential attitude. By focusing on long-term benefits, such as clean air and water, we can prioritize environmental protection over short-term gains.
9. **Critical thinking:** educational psychology can also contribute to sustainable national development by enhancing students' critical thinking skills. Critical thinking skills are important for making informed decisions about complex issues such as sustainability. Educational psychology can provide insights into the cognitive processes involved in critical thinking, such as problem-solving, reasoning, and decision-making. By teaching students' critical thinking skills, educators can help them to become informed and active citizens who are capable of making responsible decisions about sustainability.

References

- Brackett, M. A., & Rivers, S. E. (2014). Transforming students' lives with social and emotional learning. In Handbook of school-family partnerships (pp. 287-301). Routledge.
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2008). Self-determination theory: A macrotheory of human motivation, development, and health. *Canadian Psychology/Psychologie canadienne*, 49(3), 182-185.
- Durlak, J. A., Weissberg, R. P., Dymnicki, A. B., Taylor, R. D., & Schellinger, K. B. (2011). The impact of enhancing students' social and emotional learning: A meta-analysis of school-based universal interventions. *Child development*, 82(1), 405-432.
- Gardner, G. T., & Stern, P. C. (2002). *Environmental problems and human behavior*. Boston, MA: Allyn and Bacon.
- Johnson, D. W., & Johnson, R. T. (2009). An educational psychology success story: Social interdependence theory and cooperative learning. *Educational Researcher*, 38(5), 365-379.
- Kollmuss, A., & Agyeman, J. (2002). Mind the gap: why do people act environmentally and what are the barriers to pro-environmental behavior? *Environmental Education Research*, 8(3), 239-260.
- Mayer, R. E. (2014). Cognitive theory of multimedia learning. In *The Cambridge Handbook of Multimedia Learning* (pp. 43-71). Cambridge University Press.
- McKeown, R. (2013). *Education for sustainable development toolkit*. Paris, France: UNESCO.
- Sterman, J. D. (2011). Communicating climate change risks in a skeptical world. *Climatic Change*, 108(4), 811-826.
- Thogersen, J. (2012). The importance of cognitive and affective trust in communications on environmentally significant behavior. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 32(3), 277-287.
- UNESCO (2017). *Education for Sustainable Development Goals: Learning Objectives*. Paris, France: UNESCO.
- United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO). (2017). *Education for Sustainable Development Goals: Learning Objectives*. UNESCO.

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Van der Linden, S. (2015). The social-psychological determinants of climate change risk perceptions: Towards a comprehensive model. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 41, 112- 124.

Wals, A. E. J., & Corcoran, P. B. (2012). *Learning for sustainability in times of accelerating change*. Wageningen, The Netherlands: Wageningen Academic Publishers.